

THE IMPORTANCE OF BOOKS IN ELIMINATING SPEECH DEFICIENCIES IN CHILDREN

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Annotation: This article scientifically analyzes speech defects in school-age children, their types, and the importance of reading books in the development of children's speech. The article presents the results of scientific studies on the role of book reading in eliminating pronunciation problems, grammatical errors, and limited vocabulary in children, and the impact of book reading on speech development. Also, effective methods and techniques for eliminating speech defects using books are recommended.

Keywords: speech defects, children's speech, book reading, vocabulary, pronunciation, fiction, reading aloud, oral speech.

The emergence and development of speech defects in children is a complex process that depends on many factors. Speech is one of the most important abilities in a person's life as a means of thinking, acquiring knowledge and communicating. Especially in school-age children, speech is at the stage of full formation, and speech defects that arise during this period can have a significant impact on the child's later life. As a result of the widespread use of information technologies and gadgets in modern society, the culture of reading books among children is weakening. This, in turn, is causing an increase in speech defects in children. According to the results of scientific research conducted in recent years, speech defects are significantly less common in children who read books regularly. This article discusses the importance of book reading in eliminating speech defects in children, the mechanisms of the effect of book reading on children's speech, and the effective methods used in this regard. The main speech defects in children. The following speech defects are common in school-age children.

Pronunciation problems Children have problems such as pronouncing certain sounds incorrectly, replacing sounds, and omitting some sounds. These problems may arise due to the incomplete formation of the child's speech apparatus, imitating incorrect speech patterns, or not practicing systematically. Grammatical errors Among the grammatical errors that are common in children's speech are the incorrect placement of words in a sentence, the incorrect use of suffixes, and the incorrect use of pronouns. These errors are often associated with the child's insufficient mastery of the grammatical rules of the language. Limited vocabulary Limited vocabulary is manifested by the child's limited vocabulary in everyday life, inability to understand words expressing abstract concepts, and repetition of the same words. According to research, the active vocabulary of a 7-8-year-old child should contain an average of 3500-4000 words, but in many children this figure does not exceed 2000-2500 words.

Speech fluency disorders Problems such as stuttering, repetition of words, speech interruptions, and impaired speech tempo and rhythm prevent the child from freely expressing his thoughts. These problems can often be associated with psychological factors, including fear, excitement, or lack of self-confidence Logical coherence Children's speech is characterized by deficiencies such as the inability to express thoughts coherently, straying from the topic, and the inability to logically connect sentences. These problems are associated with the child's underdeveloped logical thinking ability (Ergasheva, 2021).

According to scientific research, the effect of reading on speech Reading has a multifaceted positive effect on the development of a child's speech. According to scientific research conducted in recent years, the vocabulary of children who read books regularly is 21-30% larger on average (Mahmudova, 2023). Also, children who read books make grammatical errors 2-3 times less often and they are able to express their thoughts more fluently.

Long-term studies by American scientists Cunningham and Stanovich (2001) have shown that the speech of children who develop an interest in reading at an early age develops faster later on and their level of mastery at school is also higher. In

order to develop the speech of children of preschool age, the educator conveys folk proverbs, riddles, and sayings to the child through his/her own activities. Regardless of the type of activity, the educator himself/herself should speak clearly, fluently, expressively, simply, and in a tone that the child understands. Games can leave a good impression on the child's memory. Such activities also depend on the knowledge and skills of the educator. The educator pronounces the words correctly and fluently from beginning to end of the game. The child tries to communicate not in his/her own language, but by imitating adults. A child with developed oral speech can also correctly express his thoughts. One of the main conditions for rich, meaningful speech is the correct pronunciation of the spoken word. If a child cannot pronounce some letters in words, a special specialist (speech therapist, defectologist) should work with such a child. The effect of reading books on vocabulary is that it is one of the most effective ways to expand vocabulary. In the process of reading books, the child gets acquainted with new words, understands their meaning from the context, and later learns to use them in his speech.

According to research, in every 1000 words in average-level children's literature, approximately 30-50 new words are found, which gives the child the opportunity to learn 5-10 new words every day

1. The impact of reading books on grammatical skills Through reading books, the child practically masters the grammatical structure of the language. The methods of constructing sentences and the effective use of words of writers and poets serve as an example for the child. As a result, the child develops the skills of constructing correct sentences and expressing thoughts logically and consistently in his speech. According to a study by Ergasheva (2021), grammatical errors are significantly less common in children who read books at least 3-4 times a week.

2. The effect of reading books on pronunciation Reading books aloud, memorizing poems, and expressive reading exercises help to eliminate pronunciation problems in children. In this process, the child practices pronouncing sounds correctly and develops the muscles of the speech apparatus. According to a study by Saidov (2022), children who regularly memorize poems and read books

aloud significantly reduce the problems of pronouncing difficult sounds such as "r", "l", "sh".

3. Methods for eliminating speech defects through books

1. Establishing regular book reading It is important to arouse interest in books in children and form the habit of regular book reading. To do this:

- Choose books appropriate for the child's age;
- Set aside a certain amount of time every day for reading books;
- Form a tradition of reading books in the family;
- Reading should be made an interesting activity, not an obligation.

2. Shared reading method: Reading books together with adults has a strong impact on the development of a child's speech. In this process:

- The adult shows a model of correct pronunciation and intonation;
- Explains the meaning of words;
- Talks with the child about the content of the book;
- Introduces the child to the characters of the book and exchanges opinions about them. According to a study by Mahmudova (2023), the speech of children who regularly read books together with their parents develops 18-25% better than that of their peers.

3. Reading aloud Reading aloud is an effective way to overcome pronunciation problems in children. In this process:

- The child practices pronouncing sounds correctly;
- The muscles of the speech apparatus are activated;
- The pace and rhythm of speech are improved;
- The ability to understand the content of the read text is developed.

4. Retelling poems and stories

Retelling poems and stories read from a book is one of the effective ways to develop a child's speech. During this activity:

- The child develops his memory by remembering and retelling the text he has read;
- Activates vocabulary by telling stories in his own words;
- Forms the skill of coherently describing events.

5. Creative activities based on books Conducting various creative activities based on books develops the child's speech and thinking skills:

- Talking about the characters of the book;
- Coming up with a continuation of the story;
- Depicting the events in the book through scenes;
- Drawing pictures based on the book and telling stories about them.

6. Choosing the right book To eliminate speech defects in children, it is important to choose books that are appropriate for their age, interests, and level of speech development. The following books are recommended for developing children's speech:

- Poetry collections (poems based on sound repetition);
- Fairy tales and stories (written in simple language, with an interesting plot);
- Collections of riddles and quick sayings (to practice pronunciation);
- Picture dictionaries and encyclopedias (to expand vocabulary).

Conclusion The importance of reading books in eliminating speech defects in children is incomparable. Reading books expands a child's vocabulary, develops grammatical skills, helps to eliminate pronunciation problems, and forms the ability to express thoughts coherently. In the conditions of the widespread use of information technologies and gadgets in modern society, the formation of a reading culture in children requires special attention. In this regard, the joint efforts of parents, teachers, and specialists are important. Based on the results of scientific research, it can be said that regular reading is one of the most effective ways to eliminate speech defects in children. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to reading books in the educational process, instill a love of books in children, and form a reading culture.

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